

Content Validity Testing of Items for Determining the Appropriateness of a Computer Science-Specific Learning Taxonomy Instrument

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Abstract

Classification of learning objectives using taxonomies can substantially impact teaching and learning processes if the classifications are appropriate to the subject being taught. There is currently a trend toward the development of computer science-specific taxonomies. However, a tool for determining a new taxonomy's appropriateness does not exist yet due to a lack of agreement regarding the appropriateness of a taxonomy. The purpose of this study was to determine the content validity of an instrument for assessing the appropriateness of a computer science-specific taxonomy. Five individuals specializing in computer science instruction judged the content validity of individual items on a four-point scale. These experts recommended minor revisions to improve the clarity or wording of the items, and these suggestions were incorporated into the instrument. The individual content validity index (I-CVI) and scale content validity index (S-CVI) were calculated. All the I-CVIs were 1.0, and the average scale content validity index was 1.0. The panel determined that all the items possessed sufficiently high content validity. This degree of content appropriateness indicates that the next stage of instrument development can occur.

Keywords: Learning Taxonomy; Appropriateness; Instrument Development; Content Validity Index.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Learning taxonomies are useful planning tools for instructors, helping them to assess curriculum and related educational objectives. With respect to computer science, educators have widely used Bloom's taxonomy and its revised versions [1, 2]. However, numerous other computer science-specific taxonomies have also been recommended [3-5] because of the original taxonomy's unsuitability for learning computer science subjects [6]. Teodorescu, Bennhold [7] asserted that to help educators plan and assess their teaching, taxonomies must suit their goals and include subject-specific requirements.

According to Kropp, Stoker [8], a major problem is providing evidence of a taxonomy's appropriateness including the development of a valid statistical methodology and models.

Unfortunately, there are few studies of the development of such models. Hauenstein [9] suggested five general rules of taxonomy evaluation: it should be applicable, inclusive, consist of categories that are independent from one another, reflect a consistent order, and use terms that are relevant to the subject

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area. Inclusivity prevents standards from being omitted, and mutual exclusivity prevents overlapping categories in a taxonomy.

The purpose of this study was to determine the content validity of an instrument to assess the appropriateness of a computer science-specific taxonomy. The results address the existing knowledge gap, and this instrument will provide computer science educators with a reliable, valid, and convenient tool for selecting the best taxonomy to use in their teaching practices.

2.0 TAXONOMY APPROPRIATENESS

When describing the appropriateness of a taxonomy, one must first determine the subject-specific specifications of the taxonomy. To our knowledge, no studies have discussed these specifications in relation to computer science.

To address this gap in the literature, the authors reviewed 40 studies of the application of Bloom's taxonomy in computer programming courses. The aim was to answer the following key research questions: What are the deficiencies affecting currently used learning taxonomies with regard to computer-programming courses?

To answer this question, qualitative content analysis techniques were used to analyze statements about the computer programming-related shortcomings of Bloom's taxonomy. These shortcomings were used to develop specifications for the appropriate computer science-specific learning taxonomy. Since the current adoption of Bloom's taxonomy by ACM and IEEE Computer Society [10] to categorize the learning results of the basic programming course in the prospectus of the ACM/IEEE-CS, this search was limited to investigating the weaknesses of the original Bloom's taxonomy and its revised versions. However, this analysis may also indicate other weaknesses in existing Bloom-based taxonomies.

The next sub-section describes the study performed to identify the specifications of a computer science-specific taxonomy and the dimensions required to evaluate the appropriateness of this learning taxonomy.

2.1 Specifications Identification

The literature review in this investigation involved the use of search terms that were derived from the research question, for example, "taxonomies of learning", "Computer science education", "computer programming", and "Bloom's taxonomy". This data mining involved the use of four major electronic databases: the ACM Digital Library, ScienceDirect, Springer, and Google Scholar. The title, abstract, and keywords were reviewed in the search for published journal papers, conference proceedings, workshops and excerpts from the relevant literature.

A qualitative content analysis was conducted using the NVivo version 10 qualitative software database (QSR International Pty Ltd, Burlington, MA, USA) and was guided by the procedure of Edwards-Jones [11] to partially automate our analysis of the discussion sections in the reviewed articles.

In particular, one of the authors performed a constant comparison analysis [12] of both deductive and inductive coding approaches [13]. In the deductive phase, the aforementioned rules by Hauenstein [9] were considered. This step was performed by reading the entire set of data. Then, the author chunked the data into smaller meaningful parts. The author then labeled each chunk with a descriptive title or a “code”. NVivo was used to highlight segments of the text that included coding representing a specific weakness. Each new chunk of data was then compared with previous codes so that similar chunks were labeled with the same code. After all the data were coded, the codes were grouped by similarity, and a theme was identified and documented based on each grouping.

As a result, comprehensive computer science-specific taxonomy specifications are proposed, namely, consistency, inclusivity, hierarchical adequacy, representativeness, usability, coherence, mutual exclusivity, and dimensional adequacy. Table 1 presents these primary dimensions along with the approach used and their descriptions.

To ensure inter-rater reliability, the data were coded first. Themes and randomly selected sample statements related to these themes were then given to two reviewers who had taken a course in qualitative research methods. The reviewers were Ph.D. holders in education whose research interests included computer science education. The reviewers were asked to code the documents based on the themes. The agreement between the two experts' reports measured 86%.

Table 1 Computer Science-Specific Taxonomy Specifications

No	Dimension	Approach	Description
1	Usability	Inductive	The taxonomy should categorize programming learning objectives in a simple way that could break these objectives into their components (i.e. task(s) and knowledge(s)).
2	Consistency	Deductive	The taxonomy should involve a dependable classification and interpretation of programming learning outcomes. These outcomes should always be expressed the same way.
3	Learnability	Inductive	Taxonomic categories and their interpretations should be comprehensible.
4	Hierarchical adequacy	Deductive	The hierarchy of categories should effectively describe programming learning objectives.
5	Dimensional adequacy	Inductive	The taxonomy should have two distinct dimensions (knowledge types and cognitive processes) to successfully describe the constructive learning objectives of programming. According to Airasian and Miranda [14], a two-dimensional approach allows educators to create stronger objectives that address increasingly complex instruction methods.
6	Mutual exclusivity	Inductive	Each learning objective should be assigned to only one category.

7	Inclusivity	Deductive	The taxonomy should include a sufficient list of all necessary programming knowledge types and skills for the user to classify all programming learning standards.
8	Representativeness	Deductive	The taxonomy should use common relevant terms to describe programming skills, knowledge types, and competencies required for each skill. The programming knowledge framework should be considered [15, 16].

3.0 INSTRUMENT DEVELOPMENT

The development process of Lynn [17] was used to guide the content development for this instrument. In this process, when content is being developed for an affective measure such as one of taxonomic appropriateness, two sub-processes occur: development and judgment. Development involves the identification of dimensions or sub-dimensions and extends to item generation and the subsequent integration of items into a suitable form, according to Lynn [17]. Judgment involves determining whether the given content and instrument are sufficiently valid [17]. According to Turner, Quittner [18], during initial instrument development, a conceptual framework should be identified. This framework should be representative so that the domain content is specific and relates to the subject area. This specificity is achieved by reviewing the related literature, during which potential items are identified. Once the preliminary scope of the taxonomy has been identified, the proposed content is analyzed to achieve a satisfactory final structure.

3.1 Conceptual Framework and Domain Content Identification

Insufficient information exists on theories of measuring taxonomy appropriateness, and no substantive literature regarding the application of theoretical validity frameworks are yet available. However, we recommended that the framework presented in Table 1 be considered when developing a learning taxonomy for computer programming purposes. In addition, the taxonomy framework presented in Table 1 should include items that are representative of the domain of computer programming and that adequately support the validity of the construction. This representativeness is achieved by using the framework to guide the selection of specific content deemed suitable for fully developing the instrument.

3.2 Identification of Items

The identification of items involved writing items for the scales. Initially, items from a previously validated questionnaire, specifically, the Measurement Scales for Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use, by Davis [19], was examined and adapted. Then, suitable items were written for each scale based on a review of the literature [3, 20-37], and these items were incorporated into the taxonomy

framework and were finally related to particular dimensions. Table 2 shows the items developed for each dimension.

Table 2 Taxonomy Appropriateness Items.

Dimension	Items
1. Usability	<p>1.1 This taxonomy is easy to use.</p> <p>1.2 This taxonomy is flexible in describing learning objectives.</p> <p>1.3 Using this taxonomy is effortless.</p> <p>1.4 This taxonomy gives me more control over the activities in my course.</p>
2. Consistency	<p>2.1 This taxonomy can be used to interpret programming learning tasks every time.</p> <p>2.2 This taxonomy can be used to interpret programming learning knowledge every time.</p> <p>2.3 This taxonomy can be used to classify programming learning outcomes every time.</p>
3. Learnability	<p>3.1 The categories in this taxonomy are comprehensible.</p> <p>3.2 The categories in this taxonomy can be clearly interpreted.</p> <p>3.3 This taxonomy is readable.</p>
4. Hierarchical adequacy	<p>4.1 The ordering of the taxonomy's skill sets appropriately reflects the programming learning process.</p> <p>4.2 The ordering of the taxonomy's knowledge types appropriately reflects the programming learning process.</p> <p>4.3 The ordering of the taxonomy's categories appropriately reflects programming learning objectives.</p>
5. Dimensional adequacy	<p>5.1 This taxonomy includes enough distinctive dimensions of knowledge that can be used to successfully describe constructive programming learning objectives.</p> <p>5.2 This taxonomy includes enough distinctive dimensions of cognitive that can be used to successfully describe constructive programming learning objectives.</p> <p>5.3 This taxonomy includes enough distinctive categories that can be used to successfully describe constructive programming learning objectives.</p>
6. Mutual exclusivity	<p>6.1 When using this taxonomy, each knowledge type required in programming learning can be assigned to a single category.</p>

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- 6.2 When using this taxonomy, each programming learning skill can be assigned to a single category.
- 6.3 When using this taxonomy, each programming learning objective can be assigned to a single category.
7. Inclusivity
- 7.1 The set of knowledge types in this taxonomy include all necessary knowledge types that students must know to perform a given programming learning task.
- 7.2 The skills in this taxonomy include all the necessary skills that students must acquire to perform a given programming learning task.
- 7.3 The knowledge types in this taxonomy include all appropriate types that students must know to perform a given programming learning task.
- 7.4 The skills in this taxonomy include all appropriate skills that students must acquire to perform a given programming learning task.
8. Representativeness
- 8.1 The categories in this taxonomy are relevant to learning computer programming.
- 8.2 The knowledge types in this taxonomy are relevant to knowledge required to perform computer programming learning tasks.
- 8.3 The skill sets in this taxonomy are relevant to skills that must be acquired by students to perform computer programming learning tasks.
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4.0 MEASURING CONTENT VALIDITY

Once the items have been generated, the validity of an item and of the overall instrument must be quantitatively determined [17]. In doing this, researchers frequently calculate a content validity index (CVI). Hambleton, Swaminathan [38] first presented this index and advocated its use in nursing research conducted by Waltz and Bausell [39].

Many factors guided the selection of this index, including its ease of calculation and understanding. In contrast, the content validity ratio (CVR) developed by Lawshe [40], for example, is easy to calculate but not as easy to interpret [41]. Another desirable quality of a content validity measure is that it yields item-level information that can be used to refine or discard items and a summary of the content validity of the overall scale [41].

The CVI is the percentage of respondents who assign an item a score of 3 or 4 on a 1–4 scale of relevance or representativeness. It has been recommended that an individual CVI (I-CVI) and a scale CVI (S-CVI) should be calculated separately and that the S-CVI be reported [39, 41-43].

Polit and Beck [42] preferred the S-CVI in cases where more content-expert panel members are involved because one hundred percent agreement is not feasible. The S-CVI is determined by averaging I-CVI scores. When six or more experts are involved, Lynn [17] recommended a minimum I-CVI of 0.78.

However, Waltz and Bausell [39] recommended a minimum S-CVI value of 0.90 for a valid scale in which items should be retained. In this study, we use both the I-CVI and S-CVI to determine the content validity of statements related to taxonomy appropriateness.

4.1 Expert Panel

Lynn [17] argued that at least three experts should be consulted when performing content validation. Our expert panel included five subject matter experts with more than 10 years of teaching programming experience. These experts were invited to evaluate the content validity based on the I-CVI and S-CVI. Each respondent received an informational email that included a hyperlink to a questionnaire. Survey security was maintained using Secure Sockets Layer technologies to protect confidentiality, and no personal identifiers were collected. A four-point scale was used to evaluate the content validity, and the values were matched with verbal descriptions of taxonomic appropriateness as follows: 1 = the item is not representative; 2 = the item requires major revisions to be representative; 3 = the item requires minor revisions to be representative; 4 = the item is representative. The CVI was calculated as the percentage of experts who selected 3 or 4 when scoring the items. As prescribed in the proposed methodology of our study, both the I-CVI and S-CVI were calculated. The average scale CVI (S-CVI/Ave) was determined from all the I-CVI values. The target SCVI/Ave value, according to Polit and Beck [42], is 0.9.

For greater reliability, we then calculated a modified kappa statistic (κ^*) described by Polit, Beck [41]. According to Wynd, Schmidt [44], the kappa statistic is an important supplement to the CVI because it indicates the degree of agreement beyond chance. To assess the degree of agreement based on the value of κ^* , the guidelines by Landis and Koch [45] are used.

5.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Five experts (1 female) agreed to participate in the study. The expert panel consisted of two domain experts, each with more than six years of programming teaching experience. Additionally, three members of the panel had more than 11 years of experience, and two had more than 15 years of experience. The experts currently teach programming and are familiar with the classification of learning objectives in accordance with Bloom's taxonomy. The panel was given an opportunity to provide feedback on whether they identified mistakes or ambiguities in any part of the instrument. They were also encouraged to suggest ways to improve the instrument.

According to Polit and Beck [42], the I-CVI of a new instrument should range between 0.78 and 0.80. As indicated, all the I-CVI scores for this instrument were 1.0. Therefore, all the items were retained in the questionnaire. Following the recommendations of Lynn [17], testing of a psychometric instrument should be conducted next. The expert panel assigned the instrument I-CVI scores of 1.0 (Table 3). Thus, the S-CVI/Ave value was recorded as 1.0, confirming that each individual item can be retained. The 26 items received an I-CVI value of 1.0. Because the CVI scores were consistently high, we concluded that none of the experts' suggestions regarding item content needed to be adopted. The high degree of concurrence regarding taxonomy appropriateness among the respondents indicates that the instrument for

assessing taxonomy appropriateness is adequate for progression to the next step of instrument development.

A modified kappa statistic (k^*) was calculated to determine if there was agreement between the raters' judgments regarding whether the 26 items regarding taxonomy appropriateness were relevant. There was high agreement between the five raters' judgments of all the items: $\kappa^* = 1.0$.

Table 3 Content validity indices (I-CVI and S-CVI)

Items	I-CVI	S-CVI/ave	k^*	No. of Respondents
1. Usability				
1.1 This taxonomy is easy to use.	1.0		1.0	5
1.2 This taxonomy is flexible in describing learning objectives.	1.0		1.0	5
1.3 Using this taxonomy is effortless.	1.0		1.0	5
1.4 This taxonomy gives me more control over the activities in my course.	1.0		1.0	5
2. Consistency				
2.1 This taxonomy can be used to interpret programming learning tasks every time.	1.0		1.0	5
2.2 This taxonomy can be used to interpret programming learning knowledge every time.	1.0		1.0	5
2.3 This taxonomy can be used to classify programming learning outcomes every time.	1.0		1.0	5
3. Learnability				
3.1 The categories in this taxonomy are comprehensible.	1.0		1.0	5
3.2 The categories in this taxonomy can be clearly interpreted.	1.0		1.0	5
3.3 This taxonomy is readable.	1.0		1.0	5
4. Hierarchical adequacy				
4.1 The ordering of the taxonomy's skill sets appropriately reflects the programming learning process.	1.0		1.0	5
4.2 The ordering of the taxonomy's knowledge types appropriately reflects the programming learning process.	1.0		1.0	5
4.3 The ordering of the taxonomy's categories appropriately reflects programming learning objectives.	1.0		1.0	5
5. Dimensional adequacy				
5.1 This taxonomy includes enough distinctive dimensions of knowledge that can be used to successfully describe constructive programming learning objectives.	1.0		1.0	5

5.2 This taxonomy includes enough distinctive dimensions of cognitive that can be used to successfully describe constructive programming learning objectives.	1.0	1.0	5
5.3 This taxonomy includes enough distinctive categories that can be used to successfully describe constructive programming learning objectives.	1.0	1.0	5
6. Mutual exclusivity			
6.1 When using this taxonomy, each knowledge type required in programming learning can be assigned to a single category.	1.0	1.0	5
6.2 When using this taxonomy, each programming learning skill can be assigned to a single category.	1.0	1.0	5
6.3 When using this taxonomy, each programming learning objective can be assigned to a single category.	1.0	1.0	5
7. Inclusivity			
7.1 The set of knowledge types in this taxonomy include all necessary knowledge types that students must know to perform a given programming learning task.	1.0	1.0	5
7.2 The skills in this taxonomy include all the necessary skills that students must acquire to perform a given programming learning task.	1.0	1.0	5
7.3 The knowledge types in this taxonomy include all appropriate types that students must know to perform a given programming learning task.	1.0	1.0	5
7.4 The skills in this taxonomy include all appropriate skills that students must acquire to perform a given programming learning task.	1.0	1.0	5
8. Representativeness			
8.1 The categories in this taxonomy are relevant to learning computer programming.	1.0	1.0	5
8.2 The knowledge types in this taxonomy are relevant to knowledge required to perform computer programming learning tasks.	1.0	1.0	5
8.3 The skill sets in this taxonomy are relevant to skills that must be acquired by students to perform computer programming learning tasks.	1.0	1.0	5
Scale	1.0		

I-CVI, individual content validity Index; S-CVI/ave, average scale content validity index; k*, modified kappa statistic

6.0 CONCLUSIONS

The responses of the expert panel of programming instructors indicate that the proposed content presents a high degree of taxonomic appropriateness. We also found consistency in terms of agreement among the respondents, indicating that progression to the next phase of instrument development can commence. The 26 items that were considered in the taxonomy appropriateness questionnaire will be psychometrically tested through a pilot evaluation using item response theory. This step will determine whether construct validity in the context of computer programming as demonstrated by the questionnaire serves as an indication of taxonomy appropriateness. The outcomes of this next stage may influence the future selection of taxonomies that are appropriate for this subject area.

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